

No linear behavior of industrial concrete shell roofs under seismic and fire loads using a Form Finding Optimization Model in Mexico City

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Abstract

In the 1960s, Félix Candela's concrete shells were an ideal structural solution for large industrial spaces in Mexico due to their aesthetic appeal and ability to span long distances with thin thicknesses. However, their use has declined, largely due to seismic risks, particularly in Mexico City, where earthquakes can cause explosions, fires, and structural failures and the lack of seismic design regulations for concrete shells has further limited their use.

This article aims to evaluate the structural behavior of concrete shell roofs through geometric optimization models ("form finding") to reduce strains and non-linear effects during seismic and fire events. The study uses finite element analysis (FEM) to perform both linear and nonlinear analyses, considering material behavior, instability, time history seismic response and creep due the temperature variations. The results show that geometric optimization reduces stresses and strains in the shells, providing a safer and more efficient structures for their construction in Mexico.

Keywords: Form-finding, optimization, concrete shells, earthquake design, creep, non-linear analysis, buckling, fire design, time-history analysis, concrete reinforcement, large deflections.

1. Introduction

Reinforced concrete shells are widely utilized in architecture for their geometric flexibility, enabling both simple and complex forms. This advancement has facilitated the construction of free-form structures, overcoming the limitations of traditional masonry-based shells. These structures are primarily used in industrial applications that require large spans and unobstructed surfaces. During the 1960s and 1970s, Mexico experienced significant growth in the construction of industrial facilities, leading to the creation of over 50 concrete shells, mainly designed by architect Félix Candela.

However, most of these shells have either collapsed, been demolished, or suffered irreversible damage due to seismic events, particularly in 1985 and 2017. Additionally, time-dependent effects, such as plastic flow and damage from fires and explosions, have contributed to their deterioration. The structural complexity, coupled with challenges like buckling, instability, and cracking due to the slenderness of shells, has led to a decline in their construction in Mexico, resulting in their exclusion from national building codes.

With advancements in technology and numerical analysis, it is now possible to address the challenges of these complex structures. This research proposes an analytical methodology for reinforced concrete shells, integrating computational techniques with classical mathematical formulations. The methodology covers geometric optimization, structural behavior under static loads, nonlinear geometric

and material effects, and considerations for accidental loads, such as seismic activity and temperature fluctuations, aiming to safely and efficiently reintroduce these structures in Mexico.

2. Form finding method

Concrete shell structures, admired for their sculptural and architectural beauty, often mirroring natural forms require meticulous analysis and complex calculations to ensure proper performance under both permanent and accidental loads. This fascination dates back to the 18th and 19th centuries, spurred by technological advancements and innovations in construction from the Industrial Revolution, which drove the quest for bold, iconic surfaces in temples, churches, halls, theaters, and other structures.

Spanish architect Antoni Gaudí's continuous study of natural geometric patterns, alongside his experiments with analog models, laid the foundation for the concept of "form finding." His work, which involved suspending threads and chains to form arches and catenaries under the influence of gravity, not only provided structural advantages but also added aesthetic value. His groundbreaking approach significantly contributed to iconic designs, most notably the "Expiatory Temple of the Sagrada Familia" in Barcelona, Spain.

Figure 1: Scale model and construction of the Basilica of the Sagrada Familia by Antoni Gaudí

Building on the exploration of natural analogies, German architect Frei Otto focused on the mechanical properties of roofs and domes. He conducted analog experiments using bubbles and soap films for geometric optimization, leading to the development of the "minimal surface" concept in "form finding" theory. As the name suggests, this concept emphasizes resource optimization in the analysis of structural morphology.

Figure 2: Models in soap films representing the minimal surface by Frei Otto

Frei Otto developed an increasingly sophisticated experimental methodology that proposed a holistic dialectic between research, form generation, resource optimization, creative processes, structural behavior, construction, and natural forces. He established the theoretical and practical foundations for spatial, pneumatic, and branched structures, among others. With the advent of numerical methods and computational solutions in civil engineering and architecture, mid-20th-century technological advancements such as the Finite Element Method, Computer-Aided Design (CAD), and Building Information Modeling (BIM) advanced the understanding of freeform shell structures through "parametrization." This technique enables the representation of complex curves (NURBS-splines) using manipulable variables and mathematical definitions. Today, this facilitates the conditioning of complex surface modeling via geometric rules and algorithms, allowing arbitrary surfaces to be optimized for

structural performance under static and dynamic loads, while accounting for geometric and material nonlinearity. Key methods involved include the Transient Stiffness Method, Force Density Method, and Dynamic Relaxation Method.

2.1. Force density method

The Force Density Method is essential in geometric optimization and structural engineering, especially for membrane structures and cable networks. Rooted in Schek's formulations, the method aims to minimize the potential strain energy of a structure or surface by determining the force distribution that satisfies equilibrium conditions. When applied to concrete shell structures, the method involves simulating a mesh that adopts the shape of a continuous membrane, discretizing it into nodes and bars that maintain equilibrium under applied external loads at the nodes. These point forces are subsequently converted into distributed loads along the bars. For the mesh to achieve three-dimensional equilibrium, the following conditions must be met:

$$s_a \cos(a, x) + s_b \cos(b, x) + s_c \cos(c, x) + s_d \cos(d, x) = p_x \quad (1)$$

Writing the direction cosine between all the points with reference to the coordinate axes result in the expression:

$$\text{direction cos} = \frac{\text{coordinate difference}}{\text{distance in space}} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{s_a}{a}(x_m - x_i) + \frac{s_b}{b}(x_j - x_i) + \frac{s_c}{c}(x_k - x_i) + \frac{s_d}{d}(x_l - x_i) = p_x \quad (3)$$

By introducing the term force density into the equations to deal with the nonlinear aspect of the equilibrium problem, also known as tension coefficients, it is defined as:

$$\text{force density} = \frac{\text{force in a bar}}{\text{stressed length of the bar}} \quad (4)$$

$$q_a(x_m - x_i) + q_b(x_j - x_i) + q_c(x_k - x_i) + q_d(x_l - x_i) = p_x \quad (5)$$

Only the formulations for the x direction are shown, assuming they are identical for the y and z directions, respectively.

Figure 3: Generic mesh and discretization of elements and loads in a generic node by WinTess Software

2.1.1. Matrix formulations

Once the general equilibrium solution for a specific three-dimensional node is determined, it is necessary to extend the mathematical formulations to solve for the static equilibrium of surfaces with arbitrary geometries and an unknown number of free and fixed nodes. To address these problems, a combination of mathematical tools is employed, including matrix formulations and graph theory, through the use of branch-node matrices and the simultaneous computation of partial derivatives via Jacobian matrices.

The relationship between nodes and branches can be described by branch theory using a matrix **C**, governed by the following rules:

$$C_{ij} = \begin{cases} +1 = & \text{if branch } j \text{ ends in node } i \\ -1 = & \text{if branch } j \text{ begins in node } i \\ 0 = & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

C does not contain a metric or geometry relationship only topology of the mesh.

$$\begin{matrix} & i & j & k & l & m \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} & a \\ & & & & & b \\ & & & & & c \\ & & & & & d \end{matrix} \quad (7)$$

Subdividing the branch-node matrix in two parts, one with the free points and the other with the fixed points and in the same manner we subdivide the vector of the coordinate points

$$C = [C_N \quad C_F] \quad (8)$$

$$x = [x_N \quad x_F] \quad (9)$$

Solving the problem in the x, y, z directions we get:

$$u = C_N x_N + C_F x_F \quad (10)$$

$$v = C_N y_N + C_F y_F \quad (11)$$

$$w = C_N z_N + C_F z_F \quad (12)$$

Defining U, V, W as the diagonal matrices of u, v, and w, respectively, as well as the length of the bars in the mesh, it can be defined as:

$$L = (U^2 + V^2 + W^2) \quad (13)$$

2.1.2. Jacobian

By writing the equilibrium equations of the force density method in matrix notation in Euclidean space and the transpose of the Jacobian operator, we obtain:

$$\left(\frac{\partial f(x_i)}{\partial x_i} \right)^T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial l_a}{\partial x_i} & \frac{\partial l_b}{\partial x_i} & \frac{\partial l_c}{\partial x_i} & \frac{\partial l_d}{\partial x_i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-(x_j - x_i)}{l_a} \\ \frac{-(x_k - x_i)}{l_b} \\ \frac{-(x_l - x_i)}{l_c} \\ \frac{-(x_m - x_i)}{l_d} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (14)$$

Using the branch node matrix, we write the Jacobian as

$$\left(\frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} \right)^T = C_N^T U L^{-1} \quad (15)$$

By introducing the force vectors **f** and the load component vector **p**, in addition to the force density in each bar **Uq=QCx**, the goal is to obtain the system of linear equations in the form:

$$C_N^T Q C_N x_N + C_N^T Q C_F x_F + p = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$D_N = C_N^T Q C_N \quad (17)$$

$$D_F = C_N^T Q C_F \quad (18)$$

Where the problem becomes a system of linear equations in the form $Ax=b$, where the three-dimensional static equilibrium can be defined for x as:

$$x_N = D_N^{-1}(p_X - D_F x_F) \quad (19)$$

3. Models Overview

3.1. Geometric description of the models

Concrete shell structures were developed using visual programming in the software "Rhinceros 3D" with the "Grasshopper" plug-in, following the force density method for a quadrangular mesh supported at its four corners, with varying force densities in the elements and central nodes. The objective was to create a double-curvature geometry primarily subjected to membrane stresses in a state of compression. Two different models were generated by altering the force density to assess the nonlinear stability and response to accidental seismic loads. The goal was to ensure proper performance for both structures while simultaneously comparing their structural efficiency based on force density.

Figure 4: Algorithm of the force density method created in Rhinceros 3D and for shell-type models

The geometric characteristics of the analyzed reinforced concrete shell-type roofs are as follows:

Table 1: Fundamental geometric characteristics in study models

	<i>Model A</i>	<i>Model B</i>
Dimensions:	30 m in span 9 m in height 10 cms in thickness	30 m span 12.5 m in height 10 cms in thickness
Boundary conditions:	Fixed at the four corners	Fixed at the four corners
Characteristics of the numerical model (FEM):	Finite element Quad8 Size of 30 cms 1780 nodes 1779 elements	Finite element Quad8 Size of 30 cms 1848 nodes 1849 elements

Figure 5: Model A (left) Model B (right) created with $q=0.50$ and $q=1.50$ respectively

3.2. Nonlinear models in materials and hysteretic model

The relevance of considering the constitutive laws of nonlinear materials lies in obtaining the structural response and the damage associated with inelastic deformations when the applied loads exceed the material's capacity. Additionally, it is essential for evaluating the increase in structural capacity due to the contribution of the reinforcement steel.

For the analysis, a simplified behavior model for concrete according to Mander (1988) is used, and for the steel, an elasto-plastic model is employed.

Figure 6: Constitutive models of nonlinear behavior of concrete (left) and steel (right) in kg/cm^2

A hysteretic model is used based on the description by Takeda et al. (1970), the model is employed to simulate the increase in bilinear post-yield stiffness through material degradation as a function of displacements.

Figure 7: Nonlinear hysteretic model of Takeda et al. (1970)

4. Nonlinear static and dynamic loads analyzed

4.1. Nonlinear static analysis

For the static analysis, the load combinations recommended by the Construction Regulations for Mexico City are used in the case of seismic actions including live load, dead load, fire load and response spectrum, the theory of large deformations is implemented to evaluate the geometric nonlinear behavior in the models.

Figure 8: Response spectrum according to Mexican regulations considering a damping of 5% (left) and temperature under fire load distribution across thickness shell (right)

Figure 9: Deformed shape of model A (right) and model (B) due to load combinations

4.2. Modal dynamic analysis

Since it is a nonlinear time-history analysis under accidental fire and seismic loads, it is essential to understand the modes of vibration of shell-type structures by solving the modal problem in the Eigenvectors form:

$$[K - \Omega^2 M] = 0 \quad (20)$$

Where K is the stiffness matrix, Ω^2 is the diagonal matrix of Eigenvalues and M is the mass matrix

The modal shapes and fundamental periods of the study models are defined as follows:

Table 2: Fundamental periods in vibration modes of the analyzed models

	<i>Model A</i>	<i>Model B</i>
<i>Mode 1 period:</i>	<i>0.29 sec</i>	<i>0.27 sec</i>
<i>Mode 2 period</i>	<i>0.28 sec</i>	<i>0.26 sec</i>

Figure 10: Modal shapes of model A in red and model B in blue in its first form (left) and second form(right)

4.3. Buckling Analysis

Due to the slenderness of shell-type elements, they are prone to exhibit geometric nonlinear problems, so the buckling analysis under critical loads was performed according to a generalized Eigenvalue problem.

$$[K - \lambda G(r)]\psi = 0 \quad (21)$$

Where K is the stiffness matrix, λ is the diagonal matrix of Eigenvalues, $G(r)$ is the geometric stiffness (P-delta) due to the load vector and ψ is the corresponding matrix of modes shapes.

The nonlinear critical buckling modes of the models and the pushover analysis are presented as follows:

Table 3: Critical load factors in nonlinear buckling of the analyzed models

	<i>Model A</i>	<i>Model B</i>
<i>Mode 1 buckling:</i>	<i>7.5 times load</i>	<i>8.2 times load</i>
<i>Mode 2 buckling</i>	<i>7.9 times load</i>	<i>9.1 times load</i>

Figure 11: Buckling deformed shapes of model A in red and model B in blue in its first form (left) and second form(right)

Figure 12: Pushover analysis under critical loads in the study models

4.4. Nonlinear time history analysis

This type of analysis is commonly used to evaluate the nonlinear dynamic response of structures under seismic loads in a step-by-step manner, solving the equations of motion as follows:

$$K \mathbf{u}(t) + C \mathbf{u}'(t) + M \mathbf{u}''(t) = \mathbf{f}(t) \quad (22)$$

Where K is the stiffness matrix, C is the damping matrix, M represents the diagonal mass matrix, and \mathbf{u} , $\mathbf{\dot{x}}$, and $\mathbf{\ddot{x}}$ are the displacements, velocities, and accelerations of the structure, respectively, with \mathbf{f} being the vector of applied forces.

Figure 13: Synthetic seismic signals used for nonlinear time-history analysis in gales units.

Figure 14: Time history maximum displacements under combination of fire a seismic load.

Figure 15: Time history hysteresis under combination of fire a seismic load in Model A.

Figure 16: Time history hysteresis under combination of fire and seismic load in Model B.

Time-history analyses under nonlinear seismic and fire loads demonstrate that geometric optimization with increased density in the design of concrete shells shows that curvature allows the models to remain in a pure membrane compression stress state, enabling the reinforced concrete to perform more efficiently under load demands.

5. Conclusion: submission of contributions

The analyses of the designed models validate the geometric efficiency of the concrete shells. By using geometric optimization models, stability issues and effects due to slenderness are reduced. Additionally, bending moments are minimized because the implementation of the force density method causes the concrete shells to work in a compression membrane state, with stability and structural damage problems only occurring in the **model A** of simple concrete.

With the proper steel design in the shells, an efficient behavior and structural safety of the shell-type covers under accidental loads from earthquakes and fire are validated.

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